

A Study of Dependence of the Slope S_v on Dielectric Constant of the Solvent Medium (*N*-Methylpropionamide-Water System)

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The dependence of the slope, S_v , of the apparent molal volume ϕv vs $\sqrt{C}$ curves on the dielectric constant of the medium has been studied for few common salts, e.g. KCl, NaNO₃, NaBr, NaCl, KBr, NH₄Br using *N*-methylpropionamide-water mixtures of varying dielectric constant. The results appear to show a strong dependence of S_v values on dielectric constant of the medium. It seems that, besides it, there may be some other factors also, yet to be ascertained, which are responsible for the nature of the slope.

THE discovery of a negative slope in ϕv vs $\sqrt{C}$ curves of NaBr and NaNO₃ in *N*-methylpropionamide (NMP) was reported by Millero¹. Similar results were later reported for NaCl, NaBr, KBr and KNO₃ in NMA² and Millero's results in NMP for NaBr and NaNO₃ were confirmed. Besides, negative slope for NH₄Br in NMP³ was obtained. The effect of varying the dielectric constant of the solvent (by adding water to it) on the nature of the slope of some common electrolytes has been examined earlier⁴ in this laboratory. It would be of interest to examine the effect of reducing the dielectric constant of NMP on the S_v of the common electrolytes in NMP. The earlier studies in methanol-water⁵, ethanol-water⁶ and NMA-water⁴ mixtures show that the slope increases and the negative slope becomes positive as the dielectric constant of the medium is reduced indicating a strong dependence of the slope, S_v of ϕv vs $\sqrt{C}$ curves on dielectric constant of the solvent medium. An attempt has been made to examine the dependence of S_v , of ϕv vs $\sqrt{C}$ curves of NaBr, KBr, NaCl, NaNO₃, KCl and NH₄Br (some with a reported negative and some with positive S_v -values in NMP) on the dielectric constant of the solvent medium (NMP-water), for the sake of comparison in this communication. Although the dielectric constants of different NMP-water mixtures do not appear to have been reported in the literature as yet, these have been estimated here, assuming linear relationship between composition and dielectric constant of the medium.

Experimental

N-Methylpropionamide (Fluka, purum) was fractionally crystallised and kept overnight on freshly ignited quicklime. It was then distilled under reduced pressure and the middle fraction of the distillate was collected. The process of purification

was repeated with the middle fraction until the electrical conductance of the sample was reduced to less than $10^{-6} \Omega^{-1}$. The solvent was stored in dark coloured bottles in a dry-box and was used, as far as possible, next day after distillation. Samples of electrolytes (B.D.H., AnalaR) used, namely, NaCl, NaBr, KBr, NaNO₃, KCl and NH₄Br, were recrystallised several times from conductivity-water, dried at 100° and then stored in a vacuum desiccator until used. Solution in pure NMP, pure water and 20, 40, 60, and 80% NMP content mixtures, were prepared on molal basis using conductivity-water and the densities of the solutions were measured with capped dilatometers as described earlier⁶. From the density data thus obtained apparent molal volumes were calculated in the usual manner⁷. The ϕv vs $\sqrt{C}$ curves were drawn in different cases. Two special cases are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 for NaNO₃ and NaBr, respectively (other Figs. are omitted). The slopes, S_v , of the ϕv vs $\sqrt{C}$ curves were calculated for each electrolyte in every mixture.

Results and Discussion

It may be noted from Figs. 1 and 2 that the ϕv vs $\sqrt{C}$ curves are straight lines, so the Masson's equation,

$$\phi v = \phi v^0 + S_v \sqrt{C}$$

would be applicable in all the cases. For NaCl, KCl, KBr and NH₄Br, the ϕv vs $\sqrt{C}$ curves have a positive slope at all compositions from pure water to pure NMP but NaNO₃ and NaBr, which give negative S_v values in pure NMP and positive in pure water, show transition from negative to positive S_v values in NMP-water mixtures. The dielectric constants of different mixtures, e.g. 20, 40, 60, and 80% NMP content are 98, 118, 137 and 156, respectively.

Figs. 1 and 2. Plots of molal volume vs $\sqrt{C}$ in NMP-water mixture for NaNO_3 and NaBr at 35° : NMP % (ϵ) - (1), 100 (176); (2), 80 (156); (3), 60 (137); (4), 40 (118); (5), 20 (98); and (6), 0 (78).

These were calculated assuming linear relationship with composition.

The ϕ_v vs $\sqrt{C}$ curve for NaBr in 60% NMP ($\epsilon=137$) is almost parallel to $\sqrt{C}$ axis which may be considered as the transition dielectric constant in this case and beyond this, all the higher NMP content mixtures appear to have negative slope as is shown in Table 1. For NaNO_3 , negative slope in pure NMP increases as more water is added and becomes positive when dielectric constant is reduced to around 125 (i.e. in about 55% water content mixture).

It may be mentioned that a negative slope for NH_4Br in pure NMP as reported earlier² is against the findings of this paper. The common salts KCl , NaCl , KBr and NH_4Br give positive slope in all the mixtures from pure water to pure NMP, the slope, however, increases slowly as the dielectric constant is decreased.

In conclusion, it may be noted that the ϕ_v is larger and the slope smaller, the higher the dielectric constant of the medium, and for KBr the values of S_V (Table 1), the largest.

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF S_V VALUES WITH DIELECTRIC CONSTANT IN NMP-WATER MIXTURES AT 35°

NMP wt %	S_V values					
	KCl	NaNO_3	NaBr	NaCl	KBr	NH_4Br
0	12.80	14.00	13.33	28.00	37.33	15.00
20	10.66	4.25	8.89	20.00	32.00	12.00
40	6.00	2.00	4.57	12.00	23.58	10.44
60	3.37	-5.00	0.00	10.32	21.33	9.33
80	2.18	-10.81	-5.45	6.67	16.00	5.60
100	1.90	-16.67	-10.67	3.08	8.24	2.67

As the results obtained are very much similar to those obtained for NMA-water system earlier⁴, further discussion may be omitted here as these have already been discussed in the earlier communication⁴.

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Comparative Study of 'Zone' Diffusion and 'Front' Diffusion

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Both 'front' diffusion and 'zone' diffusion of $^{131}\text{I}^-$ in 0.01 M KNO_3 in 2.5% agar gel obey Fick's second law. However, the rate of diffusion in 'front' diffusion is dependent on the time as well as the distance from the plane of contact whereas it is independent of the time in 'zone' diffusion.

A knowledge of diffusion coefficient of electrolytes in aqueous solutions is of fundamental interest in unravelling the intricate problems of meagerly understood ion-solvent interactions. Radiotracer technique has been a major probe, in recent years, to the studies on diffusion coefficient because of its several advantages over the conventional methods of analysis. In past, capillary¹⁻⁵, diaphragm⁶⁻¹⁰, optical¹¹⁻¹³ and conductivity^{14,15} methods were used for studying the diffusion of ions. These experimental techniques were not free from inherent problems of convection and streaming effects due to the flow of solvent. These methods require comparatively more time and rather a difficult experimental set-up. By using agar gel medium in place of diaphragm and capillary for such studies, the above shortcomings could be surmounted to a considerable extent. In 1930, Friedmann¹⁶ studied diffusion of non-electrolytes in agar gels and established a linear dependence of the diffusion coefficients on the gel concentration. Earlier work on the diffusion of electrolytes has been improved by the use of radiotracers. Thus Salvinien *et al.*¹⁷ have studied the diffusion of phosphate using ^{32}P , in gelatin gels. Their results do not follow the limiting law of Onsager and Fuoss¹⁸. Ionic diffusion in agar gel undoubtedly is influenced to some extent by the existence in the structure of fixed negative groups. In fact, agar gel has the remarkable property of immobilizing the solvent in a semi-rigid form and provides an ideal stationary medium. Here, the tracer-diffusion of $^{131}\text{I}^-$ in 0.01 M KNO_3 at 25° for 24, 48 and 72 h was studied by zone and front diffusion methods.

'Zone' diffusion :

A 1 mm zone of 2.5% bacto-agar containing 0.01 M KNO_3 labelled with $^{131}\text{I}^-$ was allowed to set in the centre of two columns of identical gel but containing the unlabelled electrolyte at the same concentration, in a 30 cm long pyrex tube of 1 cm diameter. The system was closed at both the ends and maintained at a constant temperature of 25° in

an automatically regulated thermostat for 24 h. After removal of the tube from thermostat, the gel column was withdrawn from the tube and sliced into series of 0.5 cm long samples. These samples were transferred to aluminium planchettes and carefully dehydrated in a hot air oven. The radioactivity of each sample was then counted under the conditions of constant geometry with the help of shielded G.M. counter of end-window type. A plot of activity vs the distance from the zone gives a symmetric Gaussian distribution satisfying Fick's second law,

$$C_{(x,t)} = \frac{C_0}{\sqrt{4\pi Dt}} \exp. (-x^2/4Dt) \quad (1)$$

where $C_{(x,t)}$ is the radioactivity at a distance x from the origin at time t and C_0 is the total radioactivity in the initial zone at $t=0$. A typical curve is presented in Fig. 1. From the slope of the plot

Fig 1. Tracer-diffusion of $^{131}\text{I}^-$ in 10^{-3} M KNO_3 electrolyte solution immobilized in 2.5% agar-agar gel at 25° by 'zone' diffusion method

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